

Blunt Trauma Chest Due to Tyre Blast InjuryKhrawkumar Lyngdoh¹, Manish Dewangan²¹Department of General Surgery, JLNHRC, Bhillai, Chhattisgarh, India.²Chief Consultant, MS (General Surgery), Department of General Surgery, JLNHRC, Bhillai, Chhattisgarh, India

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Abstract:

The destructive potential of tyre blast accident has received little attention in the medical literature. Fatal and severely deforming injuries have been reported. We report a case of a 50 year old mechanic who sustained chest wall injury due to blast of truck tyre while insufflation. He was having multiple fracture of ribs on both the sides. He was known case of DM, Hypertension, COPD, Peptic ulcer disease and CLD. The patient was managed initially with positive pressure ventilation and bilateral intercostal tube drainage and showed improvement. Later on, he developed sepsis and ultimately succumbed to his illness. This case report highlights the destructive potential of high energy blast in civilian society.

Keywords: Chronic Liver Diseases (CLD), Diabetes Mellitus Type-2 (DM), Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Tyre Blast Accident.

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Introduction

Blast injuries have the unparalleled capability to cause several categories of injuries extending from thermal to blunt or penetrating multi-system injuries that are life threatening. These include bomb explosions, terrorist blasts, and industrial and home-related explosions. Blast injuries of large tyres are similar to those resulting from landmine explosions but without thermal or chemical effects. Blast explosion of tyres usually occurs during vehicle servicing and more commonly affecting young mechanics.(1) We report such a case which we encountered.

Case Brief

A 50-year-old mechanic presented in emergency with pain over anterior chest wall and breathlessness. There was alleged history of trauma

due to blast of truck tyre three hours back while insufflating air in his shop. Patient was a known case of DM, hypertension, COPD, peptic ulcer disease and chronic liver disease.

On admission, patient was restless, pulse rate: 98/min, BP: 140/70 mm of Hg, SpO₂ was 86% in room air. His respiratory Rate was 40/min with paradoxical respiration. Bony crepitations were present on both chest wall laterally with decreased bilateral air entry. Per abdomen examination was insignificant.

CECT thorax/abdomen revealed fracture of 3rd – 5th ribs on the right side and fracture of 4th – 7th ribs on the left side with bilateral pleural collection and altered echotexture of liver.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Patient was immediately intubated and kept on mechanical ventilation. Intercostal chest tube drainage was done on both sides. Hemorrhagic fluid of approximately 100 ml drained from each side. Epidural catheter insertion was done for adequate analgesia.

Initially, the patient showed improvement and was extubated after 72 hours. But subsequently he went into hepatic decompensation due to chronic liver disease and developed ascites which further compromised his respiration. He was again re-intubated and kept on mechanical ventilation. On blood culture, *Klebsiella* was isolated. Patient went into sepsis and MODS ultimately succumbed to his illness.

Discussions

Tyre burst injuries are relatively rare but are known for causing severe injury patterns. Tyres can be thought of as air tanks, but the same safety rules that apply to pressure tanks do not apply to tyres. Blast overpressure is described as an increase in pressure above atmospheric values, as witnessed in a blast of explosive weapons. Air compression before the blast wave accelerates air molecules and generates a pressure peak. This high pressure lasts milliseconds before dropping to sub-atmospheric levels and returning to ambient pressure and is referred to as a shock wave [2,3]. Tyre blast injuries can be primary, secondary or tertiary. Primary injuries are due to shock wave that can produce severe barotrauma leading to eye injuries and damage to air containing organs such as the lung, ear drum, and nasal sinuses [4,5]. Secondary injury are caused due to flying objects coming off from the tyre like locking rings and tyre rims which can lead to significant traumas to the body, and while tertiary injury are caused when the patient is thrown away against the ground, surrounding wall or objects resulting in contrecoup pattern of injuries.

A 63000 ft-lb of energy is estimated to be released when a truck tyre is inflated to 90 psi causing it to

explode. The estimated force is around 2000 g, which is enough to raise a 3000 lb car 21 ft off the ground [6].

Most of the tyre blast injury occur during repairing or servicing a large tyre. Most of the affected individuals were reported to be younger mechanics or drivers. Very few cases of tyre blast injury have been reported and its immense potential to cause significant morbidity and mortality needs to be addressed as necessary actions can be taken to prevent such a risk.

In our study, we have a case of tyre blast injury with bilateral multiple ribs fracture with bilateral hemothorax who ultimately succumbed to his injuries following hepatic decompensation owing to chronic liver disease. This case is likely to be a primary type of blast injury since the patient had no associated external injuries in the body. In a study by Ashraf F. Hefny et al., two out of seven patients who sustained multiple injuries following tyre blast explosion, were documented to have multiple rib fractures.[7]

In another study by Rajesh Kumar et al., examination and autopsy findings of thorax of a 49 years old male patient had bilateral hemothorax and bilateral pulmonary contusions. Contusion was appreciated at the base of the heart and the origin of the aorta.[8]

In a study by Baris Hekimoglu, a 37 years old male patient had hemopneumothorax and seven rib fractures at the left hemithorax and contusions at the apex of right lung following tyre blast injury while trying to check the pressure of the tyre by hitting it with a hammer. [9]

In the case reported by O.P. Murty et al., a victim 18 years old female student sustained fractures of the ribs along with rupture of tympanic membrane and contusion of both lungs resulting in haemopneumothorax. [10]

Our case highlights the seriousness of a tyre blast accident. Preventive measures should be the main

goal so as to avoid or reduce the morbidity and mortality rates. Increasing the public awareness, establishing standards for training in workplace and adequate equipment usage during servicing large vehicle tyres are essential. [11]

Conclusion

In summary, the high energy produced by large tyre blasts may cause severe injuries leading to high morbidity and mortality. Increasing the awareness of this serious problem is essential. Prevention should be our ultimate goal.

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